

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRES MODIFIED BY ELECTROLYTIC OXIDATION AND AIR PLASMA TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Characterisation of the fibre structure builds the base for a better understanding of fibre/matrix interaction as well as fibre/size interaction. This project aims to exercise control over the interphase formation on the molecular level to change the currently strong and brittle bond to a strong and elastic bond. Fibres for this project were sourced from the Carbon Nexus facility at Deakin University, which included in-line oxidation and sizing.

A comparative study between electrolytic oxidation and air plasma treatment has been performed. Three different currents were applied to the electrolytic oxidation bath in ammonium bicarbonate and compared to air plasma treatments at different RF-powers. Both fibre treatments were compared to untreated/unsized fibres and surface treated/sized fibres. The effects on the mechanical properties were analysed by tensile tests. XPS and SEM assessed surface chemistry and surface morphology respectively.

SEM images of the untreated fibres showed the presence of carbon material in the fibre grooves that was removed by both the electrolytic oxidation and the air plasma treatment. Mechanical properties of the fibres were not affected for the optimised surface treatment current and only the highest plasma power decreased the fibre tensile strength from 3.3 GPa to 2.7 GPa. XPS analysis showed an increase in surface oxygen from 3 % for the untreated fibres to 20 % for the electrolytic bath and 10 % for the air plasma treatment. C1s curve fitting was performed and an amide/carbonyl rich surface was found after electrolytic oxidation with no acid groups on the surface. The air plasma treatment introduced acid/ester groups, amide/carbonyl groups and amine/ether/alcohol groups. Single fibre fragmentation tests showed a decrease in fragmentation length from 1000 μm for the untreated fibres to 290 μm after surface treatment and to 310 μm after air plasma treatment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Enhancement of the mechanical properties of carbon-fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) has been a research goal since the implementation of composite materials in the 1960's [1]. Despite the increased use of composites in recent years there are still uncertainties surrounding the detection of damage sites, failure models and the fundamental understanding of the fibre/matrix interaction [2].

The characterisation of the carbon-fibre surface properties is essential to gain a better understanding of the processes taking place during surface treatment, sizing and fibre/matrix interaction. With the development of carbon-fibre composites, it became obvious that the untreated

fibres poorly bonded to the matrix material [3]. Hence, different surface treatment methods were investigated and electrolytic oxidation in ammonium bicarbonate won the race for best electrolyte. Oxidation of the fibre surface was greatly reduced compared to more aggressive electrolytes like nitric acid and no residue was left on the fibre surface [4]. This process was easily incorporated in the production line, fast and suited the industrial needs of mass production.

The current carbon-fibre production includes a surface treatment in an electrolytic bath followed by washing and drying of the fibres before pulling them through a resin emulsion (size) and drying them again. The size protects the fibre surface during subsequent processing steps. Changing the production to a dry process would eliminate the use of water as well as the need to dry the fibres, making it more environmentally friendly. Air plasma is one option for a dry process that could also be incorporated into the production line when performed in atmosphere. Studies on air plasma treatments under reduced pressure showed that air plasma had a similar effect to electrolytic oxidation under optimised conditions [5].

In this study, fibres from different stages of the production line were analysed to understand the effects of surface treatment and the sizing on the surface morphology, the surface chemistry and the mechanical properties

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Carbon-fibre manufacturing

Despatch Industries manufactured the carbon-fibre production line in collaboration with Furnace Engineering Pty. Ltd. Carbon fibres were produced by the Carbon Nexus research facility at Deakin University especially for this project.

A scaled down single tow line was used for fibre production. The precursor (Bluestar, 24k, China) was stabilised in four oxidation ovens that heated the fibres from 228 °C to 258 °C in 10 °C increments using a drive speed of 30 m/h. After the oxidation ovens the fibres passed through the low temperature furnace which included three zones. The temperatures in the three zones were set to 450 °C, 650 °C and 850 °C, respectively. In the carbonization oven the fibres passed through two zones where they were heated to 1200 °C and finally 1400 °C.

The first samples were taken after the carbonization oven without further surface treatment or sizing. To protect the fibres during the spooling process, Kapton tape (GMS Composites, Dandenong, Australia) was used as a protective layer.

The second samples passed through the surface treatment bath which was filled with ammonium bicarbonate (Consolidated Chemicals Co., Dandenong South, Australia) as the electrolyte. The conductivity of the treatment bath was kept constant at 19.7 mS/cm and three treatment currents were applied to analyse the effects on the fibre properties. The treatment currents were set to 2.8 A, 4.8 A and 6.6 A. After the surface treatment bath the fibres were rinsed with water and dried at 180 °C. Kapton tape was included in the spooling process.

The third samples were surface treated at 4.8 A, washed, dried, sized (EP834, Michelman, USA) and dried again at 180 °C before the spooling process. No Kapton tape was included as the size acted as a protective coating.

A pure sizing sample was prepared on a silicon wafer by mixing size with deionized water (1:10) and dried at 180 °C.

2.2 Plasma Treatment Process

Plasma treatments were performed in a custom build plasma reactor with the majority of parts purchased from LewVac Components Ltd., UK. The plasma chamber consisted of a stainless steel 'ISO-200 Tee' with three 'ISO-200' flanges sealed with centering-rings including Viton o-rings. The flanges were equipped with various 'KF' flange stubs to connect the pirani pressure gauge (APG100XLC-KF16, Edwards Ltd., UK), needle valve (CMV-VFM-3-P-KK, Chell Instruments Ltd., UK), air admittance valve, vacuum pump and view port. An aluminium disc-electrode (D=170 mm) was located inside the reactor chamber, connected to a coaxial type-n feedthrough and mounted to a stainless steel rod that allowed positioning of the electrode inside the chamber. The plasma was ignited

by a RF-generator (RFG100-13, Coaxial-Power-Systems-Ltd., UK) with a radio frequency of 13.56 Hz. A manual matching network (MMN150, Coaxial-Power-Systems-Ltd., UK) was used to minimise the reflective index and ensure that the power input was equal to the power output at the electrode. The vacuum system consisted of a cold trap with two z-line valves and an Edwards RV12 rotary vane pump.

The general steps for setting up the plasma run included filling the cold trap with liquid nitrogen, evacuating the plasma chamber to a base pressure of $< 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar followed by a leak test. An empty run was performed to ensure the right setting of the matching network for the chosen power input. Air plasma runs were performed at various plasma powers (5 W to 100 W) for 5 min. The gas flow was maintained for further 5 min after turning of the plasma power to allow free radicals to be quenched.

The air plasma run was performed on untreated/unsized carbon-fibres. Approximately 10 cm of carbon-fibre tow was cut from the spool and fixed to an aluminium sample holder. The sample holder was placed 4.5 cm away from the electrode.

2.3 Characterisation of surface chemistry

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was performed using an AXIS Nova (Kratos Analytical Inc., Manchester, UK) with a source energy $h\nu$ of 1486.6 eV. The machine is equipped with a monochromated Al K_{α} source and a hemispherical analyser operating in fixed analyser transmission (FAT) mode. Carbon fibre samples were suspended 8 mm above the sample plate using two custom made aluminium bars to ensure that only the carbon fibres were analysed and not the sample platen underneath the fibres. No special preparation of the carbon-fibres prior to XPS analysis was performed.

The x-ray spot size was set to ‘slot’ which measures approximately 700 μm x 300 μm . The total pressure in the sample analysing chamber (SAC) during analysis was typically below 10^{-8} mbar. The photoelectron emission angle was set to 0° which corresponds to a 90° take-off angle measure from the fibre axis. For the survey scan the pass energy was set to 160 eV with a scan time of 2 min and 1 sweep. The high-resolution scan for C1s, O1s and N1s was obtained with a pass energy of 20 eV, a scan time of 90 sec and 3 sweeps. Three points per sample were analysed to calculate an average distribution. No charge neutraliser was used.

Casa XPS software version 2.3.15 (Casa Software Ltd., Teignmouth, UK) was used for data processing. Element quantification was based on standard relative sensitivity factors provided by the manufacturer. The elemental composition on the surface was identified from the survey spectrum while the chemical states associated with each element were assessed from the high-resolution spectra. Six components were fitted to the high resolution C 1S scan of the *UT+US* fibres and propagated for the entire sample range except for the sized fibres. The curve fitting of the high resolution data was performed using the line shapes, full width half max constraints (fwhm) and position constraints shown in Table 1.

	sp2	sp3	Amine/Ether/ Alcohol	Amide/ Carbonyl	Acid/Ester	Plasmon
<i>Line shape</i>	LA(1,3,0)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)	GL(30)
<i>fwhm constraint</i>	0-2	0-2	0-2	0-2	0-2	0-2.5
<i>Position constraint</i>	-	284.8-285	285.9-286.6	287.9-288.3	288.9-289.1	290.5-292

Table 1: Line shape, full width half maximum (fwhm) constraints and position constraints for the curve fitting of the high resolution C1s spectra.

The first component was the sp2 peak and an asymmetric line shape (LA(1,3,0) with no position constraints. The peak for all samples positioned itself in the binding energy range of 284.2 eV. All

other components were fitted using a Gaussian Lorentzian line shape (GL(30)) and the positions were constraint according to literature [6].

2.4 Surface topography

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to analyse the surface morphology of the carbon fibres after different treatment conditions. A Supra 40VP (Carl Zeiss AG, Germany) FE-SEM was used. Small bundles of fibres were spread out on carbon tape and fixed with pressure. Pressurised air was used to ensure no loose fibres were present and possible contaminants were removed. The samples were gold coated for 50 sec at 30 mA. The images were taken at a magnification of 20000 and a beam current of 3 kV using the second electron detector.

2.5 Tensile test

Tensile tests of single carbon-fibres were conducted on a Favimat + Robot 2 (Textechno H.Stein, Germany). The machine automatically loads and tests the single fibres. A pretensioning weight was attached to the bottom of each fibre before it was loaded into a magazine that could hold up to 25 filaments. The fibres were collected at random and care was taken to not inflict damage to the fibre surface. A minimum of 60 fibres was tested for each fibre type.

The machine automatically measured the linear density and force-extension curve for each fibre. Linear density measurements were undertaken according to ASTM D 1577 using the vibration method. Measurement of the resonance frequency under know pretension (1.6 N) and constant gauge length (25 mm) allowed the calculation of the linear density T_t according to the following formula:

$$T_t = \frac{F_v}{4 \cdot f^2 \cdot L^2} \quad (1)$$

where:

- T_t = linear density
- F_v = pretensioning force
- f = resonance frequency
- L = gauge length

The specific tensile strength (tenacity) was measured in cN/tex using a gauge length of 25 mm and a loading speed of 0.5 mm/min. The specific modulus was obtained from stress-strain curves recorded during the test. Tenacity and modulus were converted into MPa/GPa by using an average fibre density of 1.8 kg/m³.

A Weibull distribution was used to calculate the mean values of tenacity and modulus, acknowledging carbon-fibres as a brittle material where surface flaws and defects in the material structure cause failure. Failure probability P was calculated using the Bernard's Median Rank's approximation. The two-parameter Weibull probability equation was used:

$$P = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (2)$$

where:

- P = cumulative probability of failure
- σ = applied tensile stress
- σ_0 = characteristic stress
- m = Weibull modulus

The Weibull modulus was obtained by linear regression and describes the probability of having critical flaws that contribute to failure. A higher Weibull modulus is a sign for less critical flaws on the surface and a more homogenous distribution of failure sites on the fibre.

2.6 Single fibre-fragmentation test

Single fibre fragmentation tests (SFFT) are a popular method to analyse the bonding behaviour of the fibre-matrix interphase. A single fibre is embedded in the middle of a resin specimen and loaded under tension. The failure strain of the fibre is relatively low compared to the matrix failure strain. This causes the fibre to fracture long before the matrix material. Load transfer between fibre and matrix is enabled through the interphase between the two constituents. After fibre fracture the tensile stress drops to zero at the fracture location. With increasing elongation of the specimen, the fibre fractures into smaller and smaller pieces. Elongation of the matrix produces shear stresses that are transferred into the fibre via the interphase, causing an increase in tensile stress. This leads to further fibre fragmentation until the fragments are too short to transfer sufficient stresses into the fibre to cause breakage. At this point the saturation fragment length is reached. Another phenomena that can take place during the fibre breakage is a peak in shear strength that causes interfacial debonding. Once the specimen has reached the saturation point the individual fragment lengths are measured and an average fragment length l is calculated. Using the following formulas it is possible to calculate the critical fragment length l_c and the interfacial shear strength τ :

$$l_c = \frac{4}{3}l \quad (3)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f(l_c) \cdot d}{2 \cdot l_c} \quad (4)$$

where:

- l_c = critical fragment length
- l = average fragment length
- τ = interfacial shear strength
- σ_f = fibre strength at critical length l_c
- d = fibre diameter

Tensile tests of single fibres are required to calculate σ_f by using a Weibull distribution, as described in 2.5. A single fibre was embedded in a polymer matrix (RIM 935 + RIM 937), cured on the bench top for two days and then cured for 16 h at 100 °C under vacuum. The chosen polymer had a sufficiently higher failure strain than the fibre. Specimens were tested on an Instron with a constant test speed of 0.05mm/min until an elongation of 4-6% was reached. Tested specimens are placed under a light microscope to measure the fragmentation length and calculate the average fragmentation length l . Assessment of the stress state of the interphase is possible by using cross-polarised light. The fracture zone around the fibre break appears as a coloured pattern and allows to make statements about the interphase debond process.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Influence of surface treatment on the fibre morphology

Commercial surface treatment at different treatment currents

Analysis of the SEM images collected from the fibres showed that the surface morphology was influenced by the current applied to the surface treatment bath (see Figure 2). Fibre diameter was relatively consistent across the fibres (6 μm to 8 μm), but the variations made it impossible to assess the effect of surface treatments on the fibre diameter. All fibres showed the grooves and ridges typical of PAN based fibres. The extent to which the grooves and ridges were visible depended on the treatment conditions. *UT+US* fibres had less pronounced grooves and small cracks were visible on the surface, pointing out the existence of a carbon material present in the grooves. A treatment current of 2.8 A resulted in a surface covered with agglomerations. Deeper grooves were visible for parts of the fibre surface while other fibres appeared with less pronounced grooves than the untreated fibres. The low current appeared to redistribute the material present in the fibre grooves onto the surface.

Figure 2: SEM images of carbon fibre surfaces before surface treatment, after surface treatment and after surface treatment and sizing.

Fibres treated at 4.8 A and 6.8 A both appeared clean and smooth with deeper grooves and ridges compared to the *UT+US* fibres.

ST+S fibres also had a clean and smooth appearance with less pronounced grooves, possibly do to the size getting pulled into the cavities. It was expected that the fibres would have a thicker sizing layer on the surface. After sizing, the fibres did not show the same handleability as commercially sized fibres, possibly due to the thin sizing layer.

Air plasma treatment of carbon fibres

The air plasma process influenced the surface morphology of the carbon fibres, but there were no apparent differences visible for the different plasma powers applied.

Figure 3: SEM images of air plasma treated carbon-fibres using various plasma powers.

The image of the 60W air plasma was chosen to show the removal of a loosely bound layer of material from the fibre surface.

Figure 3 shows the SEM images of the fibre surfaces after 5 min of air plasma. The material that was visible on the *UT+US* fibres has been removed, but small agglomerations were visible all over the fibre surface. Plasma processes are always a combination of etching and deposition processes with one process being dominant. The agglomerations show that the removed carbon material was redeposited onto the fibre surface to some extent. A similar effect has been seen for the low current aqueous bath.

Plasma treatments have been reported to only affect the top layers of the fibre surface [7]. Hence, a higher plasma power does not necessarily increase the etch intensity or change the surface morphology significantly.

3.2 Carbon-fibre surface chemistry analysed by XPS

Commercial surface treatment at different treatment currents

The elemental composition of the five different carbon-fibre samples is given in Table 1. A drop of sizing was mixed 1:10 with deionised water and dried at 180 °C. The *UT+US* fibres revealed low levels of nitrogen, that can be explained by the PAN precursor and the nitrogen environment inside the high temperature furnace. The low amount of oxygen on the surface is representative for carbon-fibres without a surface treatment and is in agreement with the literature [8]. Surface treatments and washing of the fibres introduced traces of magnesium, chloride, calcium and sodium on the fibre surface from the rainwater used in the bath. Analysis focused on the main elements: carbon, oxygen and nitrogen. The oxygen concentration increased from 2 % for the untreated fibres to 19% and 20% for the surface treatments with 2.8 A and 4.8 A, respectively. Surface treatments performed with 2.8 A and 4.8 A also increased the nitrogen content from 1% for the untreated fibres to 3 %. At the highest applied current (6.6A), the oxygen and nitrogen content were the lowest of all three fibres.

Fibre type	% C	% O	% N	% Ca	%Mg	%Na	%Cl
<i>Pure sizing</i>	79.9	20.1					
<i>UT+US</i>	96.6	2.1	1.3				
<i>ST(2.8A)+US</i>	75.2	18.9	3.3	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.3
<i>ST(4.8A)+US</i>	73.9	20.4	3.4	1.2	0.7	0.3	0.1
<i>ST(6.6A)+US</i>	82.1	13.8	2.5	0.9	0.4	0.3	<0.1
<i>ST(4.8A)+S</i>	79.1	20.2	0.2	0.2	<0.1	0.1	0.1

Table 1: Elemental composition of the carbon-fibre surface before surface treatment, with surface treatment using three different currents and after surface treatment and sizing.

After pulling the fibres through the sizing bath, a layer of epoxy resin was applied to the surface, attenuating the surface nitrogen on the fibres treated with a current of 4.8 A. As the sampling depth of the XPS is 10 nm and only traces of nitrogen were detected, it can be concluded that the epoxy resin was close to 10 nm thick. The wide scan of the pure size had a similar elemental composition as the sized fibres.

Curve fitting of high-resolution C1s spectra was performed to compare the changes in functional groups present on the surface. By keeping the constraints for the curves consistent throughout the samples it was possible to get an idea of the changes occurring. This approach to curve fitting is semi-quantitative. Table 3 shows the surface functionalities present on the five different fibre samples. The high resolution C1s scan of the *UT+US* fibres revealed a line shape that was almost identical to pure graphene. After each of the electrolytic bath treatments, there was little change visible in the acid/ester peak for the different treatment currents. This suggests that the surface treatment bath does not incorporate carboxyl groups as previously reported in the literature [7] and a predominantly carbonyl rich surface is present. At a treatment current of 4.8 A, a sp³-carbon component appeared due to a slight peak broadening that could indicate the removal of carbonaceous material. For fibres treated at 6.6 A the carbon peak was broadened further in a way that suggested a change from sp² hybridised

carbon to a mix of sp² and sp³ hybridised carbon. This sp³-peak may indicate significant removal of carbonaceous material from the surface.

Fibre type	% sp ²	% sp ³	% Amine/Ether/Alcohol	% Amide/Carbonyl	% Acid/Ester	% Plasmon
<i>Pure sizing</i>		49	50.44			0.56
<i>UT+US</i>	88.8	-	3.7	2	0.9	4.6
<i>ST(2.8A)+US</i>	82.7	-	2.8	11.4	0.1	3
<i>ST(4.8A)+US</i>	75.6	4.1	2.7	13.3	0.1	2.5
<i>ST(6.6A)+US</i>	44	34.8	11.7	8.1	0.5	0.9
<i>ST(4.8A)+S</i>	-	48.1	49	0.9	0.8	1.1

Table 3: Relative area (%) of C1s spectra for commercially treated carbon-fibres in ammonium bicarbonate.

The peak broadening also increased the amine/ether/alcohol peak from 3 % to 12 %. Since the surface oxygen content decreased for the fibres treated at 6.6 A, it can be assumed that mainly ether functionalities were introduced

Combining the results from the wide scan with the high resolution scan allows us to make assumptions about the actual functional groups present. Looking at the fibres treated at 6.6 A the amine/ether/alcohol peak takes up 11.7% of the 82.1 % available carbon, that means 9.6 %. An alcohol would mean that for each carbon, one oxygen would be required on the surface, which would mean that at least 9.6 % oxygen is required. Since only 13.8 % oxygen is available on the surface, it can be assumed that most of the functionalities have to be ether. An ether is formed with 2 carbon atoms and one oxygen atom. That would mean that a minimum of 4.8 % oxygen is required on the surface. That leaves 9 % oxygen available for either carbonyl or acid/ester groups. These calculations allow a rough estimate of the curve fit and its plausibility.

In the C1s spectrum of the sized fibres a new peak appeared in the binding energy range of amine/ether/alcohol functionalities. Hydroxyl and ether functionalities are in the same energy range and therefore hard to distinguish, but it is clear that this data supports the interpretation that the sizing layer is close to 10 nm thick. The C1s curve of the pure size was similar to the sized fibres with small amounts of acid/ester and amide/carbonyl functionalities being visible on the sized fibres. This also suggests that the sizing layer is close to 10 nm thick and it can be concluded that the oxygen on the fibre surface is due to the sizing.

Air plasma treatment of carbon fibres

The surface composition of the air plasma treated fibres is shown in Table 4. An increase in plasma power from 5 W to 100 W lead to an increase in surface oxygen from 9 % to 12 %. The nitrogen concentration for all plasma powers stayed constant around 2 %. The plasma power seems to have no significant effect on the incorporation of oxygen onto the fibre surface.

Fibre type	% C	% O	% N
<i>UT+US</i>	96.6	2.1	1.3
<i>Air 5W</i>	88.7	9.4	1.9
<i>Air 20W</i>	89.1	9.1	1.8
<i>Air 40W</i>	88.8	9.5	1.7
<i>Air 60W</i>	87.8	10	2.2
<i>Air 80W</i>	86.8	10.8	2.4
<i>Air 100W</i>	86.4	11.9	1.8

Table 4: Elemental composition of the carbon-fibre surface after air plasma treatment at various plasma powers.

High resolution C1s scans were analysed in the same way as the commercially surface treated fibres. The surface functionalities are listed in Table 5. All plasma powers introduced similar amounts of oxygen onto the surface and similar C1s curves were visible.

Fibres treated at 20 W were the exception with a broadened amine/ether/alcohol peak and a lower sp²-carbon peak than the other fibres. Since similar amount of oxygen were introduced on all fibres, the peak broadening, which caused an amine/ether/alcohol peak of 14 %, has to be further investigated and can be seen as an outlier, most likely due to charging.

The slight increase in surface oxygen was in agreement with the slight decrease in sp²-carbon for increasing plasma power. Amine/ether/alcohol functionalities were incorporated in varying amounts ranging from 4-7 %. The amide/carbonyl and acid/ester peaks can be shifted one way or the other resulting in similar curve fits. Therefore, the numbers have to be seen as a guideline that allows us to make assumptions. Overall the air plasma introduced roughly the same amount of both functionalities on the surface and an overall increase can be seen with increasing plasma power. Compared to the commercial treatment the air plasma did introduce acid/ester groups onto the fibre surface.

The results are in disagreement with other findings in the literature [8], where more oxygen as well as nitrogen was incorporated by air plasma than by electrolytic oxidation. It is not obvious what flow rate was used during their plasma treatment which makes it hard to know the reason for the different results. The surface oxygen content might be lower because air plasma only affects the first few atomic layers. A ToFSIMS study with its higher resolution and lower sampling depth is envisioned to give an answer to this question.

Fibre type	% sp ²	% sp ³	% Amine/Ether/Alcohol	% Amide/Carbonyl	% Acid/Ester	% Plasmon
<i>UT+US</i>	88.8	-	3.7	2	0.9	4.6
<i>Air5</i>	85.5	-	4.4	2.9	4.2	3.8
<i>Air20</i>	77.6	-	14	4	2.1	2.2
<i>Air40</i>	82.8	-	6.1	3.9	3.8	3.4
<i>Air60</i>	83.5	-	4.3	3.5	5	3.6
<i>Air80</i>	82.2	-	6.4	3.5	5.2	3.2
<i>Air100</i>	80.8	-	7.5	4.4	5	2.8

Table 5: Relative area (%) of C1s XPS spectra for air plasma treated carbon-fibres.

3.3 Influence of the surface treatment on the mechanical and adhesion properties of carbon fibres

Great care was taken when choosing the fibres for the tensile test, but significant differences were noticed in the test results. To confirm the suspicion, three independent tensile runs were performed using 60 fibres for each run. Fluctuation in Weibull modulus ranged from 4.7 to 7.3. Knowing the impact of the Weibull modulus in terms of the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) calculations, it is suggested that the IFSS results have to be presented in combination with the actual failure length to get a better picture of the adhesion between fibres and resin.

Commercial surface treatment at different treatment currents

As shown in Table 6, *UT+US* fibres had a characteristic tensile strength of 3.22 GPa and a Weibull modulus of 4.33. The Young's modulus for all fibres did not differ significantly with values between 202-214 GPa. It was expected that the surface treatment should not affect the Young's modulus as it is a bulk material property that is influenced by surface flaws. The average tensile strength of the fibres is consistently lower than the characteristic tensile strength calculated with the Weibull distribution. No significant difference in average tensile strength is visible for the *UT+US*, *ST4.8* and *ST4.8+S* fibres. Tensile test results of the various different fibre samples are summarised in Table 6. Hence, optimising the treatment conditions minimises the damage to the fibres, maintaining the mechanical properties while creating a clean surface. The Weibull modulus increased after the surface treatment process and stayed similar after the sizing process. The *ST+S* fibred had similar tensile properties as

the *ST+US*. It was reported that the sizing increases the tensile properties of the fibres by filling surface flaws, but knowing that the mechanical properties of uncured epoxy resin it seems very unlikely that the sizing would contribute to tensile strength in any way.

Fibre type	σ_{average} [GPa]	E_{modulus} [GPa]	σ_0 [GPa]	Weibull modulus	L_{average} [μm]	IFSS [MPa]
<i>UT+US</i>	2.9±0.7	208.4±6.1	3.2	4.3	1030±309	18.3
<i>ST(2.8A)+US</i>	2.2±0.5	201.6±9.9	2.4	4.8	340±106	48.9
<i>ST(4.8A)+US</i>	2.9±0.5	214.2±5.7	3.1	6	286± 85	64.4
<i>ST(6.6A)+US</i>	2.7±0.6	207.4±7.7	2.9	4.8	291± 83	71.3
<i>ST(4.8A)+S</i>	3 ±0.5	209.2±5.8	3.2	6.5	294±102	61.4

Table 6: Summary of the mechanical and adhesion properties of commercially treated carbon fibres.

The low treatment current of 2.8 A and the high treatment current of 6.6 A reduced the tensile strength by 27 % and 10%, respectively. A small increase in Weibull modulus from 4.3 to 4.8 was achieved. As mentioned before the Weibull modulus is highly dependent on the person handling the fibres and not too much focus can be put on the Weibull modulus.

The single fibre fragmentation tests results are shown in Table 6. An average fibre diameter of 8 μm was used for all calculations. SEM analysis of the fibres after different treatment conditions showed no significant differences in fibre diameter. Fibre diameters ranged from 6-8 μm which is due to wet spinning of the PAN precursor. A reduction in average fragment length (L_{average}) to 1/3 of that of the *UT+US* fibres was achieved for all surface treatments. Hence, the adhesion between fibres and resin was significantly improved. No improvement can be seen for the sized fibres over the surface treated fibres.

Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) calculations are also shown in Table 6. The importance of the Weibull modulus (m) becomes obvious when comparing the fibres treated at 4.8 A and 6.6 A. Fibres treated at 4.8 A are superior to the fibres treated at 6.6 A in all aspects from σ_0 , m to L_{average} . Nevertheless the fibres treated at 6.6 A had a higher IFSS, because m was lower. A difference in m from 4.8 to 6 impacted IFSS by almost 10 %. Similar variations can be introduced through handling of the fibres. Hence, the IFSS results are a semi-quantitative measure that allows a rough comparison of fibre/matrix adhesion between different treatment methods.

Air plasma treatment of carbon fibres

A summary of the tensile test results is shown in Table 7. The characteristic tensile strength was on average 0.2 GPa higher than the average tensile strength. The same behaviour was seen with the commercially treated fibres. Based on σ_0 there tensile properties were not affected by the air plasma except for a plasma power of 100 W, where a reduction in tensile strength was visible.

Fibre type	σ_{average} [GPa]	E_{modulus} [GPa]	σ_0 [GPa]	Weibull modulus	L_{average} [μm]	IFSS [MPa]
<i>UT+US</i>	2.9±0.7	208.4±6.1	3.2	4.3	1030±309	18.3
<i>Air 5</i>	3.1±0.5	214.1±6.6	3.3	7.3	414±141	40.0
<i>Air 20</i>	2.8±0.6	211.5±6.6	3.1	4.7	310± 99	71.1
<i>Air 40</i>	2.8±0.5	212.7±8.9	3	5.8	346±104	51.2
<i>Air 60</i>	3 ±0.7	207.7±7.7	3.3	5.2	357±100	58.9
<i>Air 80</i>	3.2±0.6	210.8±6.3	3.4	5.8	559±171	33.4
<i>Air 100</i>	2.5±0.5	209.2±6	2.7	5.5	276± 77	64.0

Table 7: Summary of the mechanical and adhesion properties of commercially treated carbon fibres.

A Weibull modulus of 7.3 was calculated for the fibres treated at 5 W. That was the highest Weibull modulus achieved for any of the fibre samples. The big jump in Weibull modulus raised the question on how much impact handling of the fibres had on the overall results.

Average fragments lengths and IFSS are shown in Table 7. Air plasma treated fibres had slightly longer L_{average} than the commercially treated fibres, but no significant difference can be seen with regard to standard deviation. IFSS values reached values similar to the commercially treated fibres. This in agreement with the literature where no correlation between oxygen/carbon ratio and the IFSS was found [7].

4 Summary and Conclusion

The effects of different surface treatment conditions have been analysed using SEM, XPS, tensile tests and single fibre fragmentation. SEM analysis showed the presence of a material layer on the *UT+US* fibres. Removal of this loosely bound carbon material was achieved with both treatment methods. Commercial surface treatment in ammonium bicarbonate showed better cleaning results than the air plasma. Surface treatment in ammonium bicarbonate introduced up to 20 % oxygen in form of carbonyl and ether functionalities that have little contribution to covalent bond formation. No carboxyl groups were present on the surface as mentioned in the literature. Air plasma introduced 10 % of oxygen on the surface including acid/ester groups.

Mechanical properties of the fibres were retained for both treatment methods. Optimisation of the treatment conditions was more crucial for the aqueous bath than for the air plasma treatment, which supports the findings in the literature. It was reported that plasma treatments only affect the top layers of the fibre, making it a less damaging process.

Both treatments reduced the average fragment length to 290-300 μm compared to 1000 μm for the *UT+US* fibres even though one treatment introduced twice as much oxygen on the surface as the other. It was claimed that carboxyl and hydroxyl groups play a major role in fibre/matrix adhesion, but no carboxyl groups were found and hydroxyl groups were present as ethers with little reactivity. Hence, removal of the loosely bound carbon material and increasing the surface area seem to be the main contributors for fibre/matrix adhesion. Polarity of the fibre surface has not been analysed but might play an important role as well. The sizing layer did not change the mechanical or the adhesion properties of the fibres. For the size used in this study, diffusion into the matrix material without an interphase formation is the most likely scenario. In this case, sizing provides protection of the fibre surface and better handleability of the fibre tow. Hence, the surface treatment step is the only contributor to the fibre matrix interaction. Further research is necessary to analyse if amine containing functionalities can improve the fibre matrix adhesion through covalent bonding.

Weibull distribution was used to calculate the characteristic fracture stress σ_0 and the Weibull modulus m . Fibre handling had significant effects on the tensile results and even more significant effects on the Weibull modulus. Both parameters are directly related to the IFSS and it is therefore recommended to analyse IFSS values in combination with the fracture length. The author recommends the development of a procedure for fibre extraction from the tow to ensure more reliable test results and comparability of results from independent groups.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L.T. Drzal. The role of the fiber-matrix interphase on composite properties. *Vacuum*, **41**: 1990, pp. 1615–1618 (doi:[10.1016/0042-207X\(90\)94034-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-207X(90)94034-N)).
- [2] G. Marsh. The challenge of composite fuselage repair. *Reinforced Plastics*, **56**, 2012, pp. 30–35 (doi: [10.1016/S0034-3617\(14\)70085-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-3617(14)70085-2)).
- [3] D.A. Jesson and J.F.Watts, The Interface and Interphase in Polymer Matrix Composites: Effect on Mechanical Properties and Methods for Identification. *Polymer Reviews*, **52**, 2012, pp. 321–354 (doi: [10.1080/15583724.2012.710288](https://doi.org/10.1080/15583724.2012.710288)).
- [4] J.D.H. Hughes, The carbon fibre/epoxy interface - a review. *Composites Science and Technology*, **41**, 1991, pp. 13-45 (doi :[10.1016/0266-3538\(91\)90050-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(91)90050-Y)).
- [5] C. Jones and E. Sammann, The effect of low power plasmas on carbon fibre surfaces. *Carbon*, **28**, 1989, pp. 509-514 (doi:[10.1016/0008-6223\(90\)90046-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0008-6223(90)90046-2)).
- [6] Beamson G, Briggs D. *High resolution XPS of organic polymers—the Scienta ESCA300 database*, Wiley, Chichester, 1992.
- [7] C. Jones, The chemistry of carbon fibre surfaces and its effect on interfacial phenomena in fibre/epoxy composites, *Composites science and technology*, **42**, 1991, pp. 275–298 (doi: [10.1016/0266-3538\(91\)90021-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(91)90021-G)).
- [8] K.E. Atkinson, G.J. Farrow, and C. Jones, Study of the interaction of carbon fibre surfaces with a monofunctional epoxy resin, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **27**, 1996, pp. 799–804 (doi: [10.1016/1359-835X\(96\)00030-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/1359-835X(96)00030-9)).